

FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CLOTRIMAZOLE ORO-RETENTIVE GUMMIES FOR THE TREATMENT OF ORAL CANDIDIASIS (ANTI-FUNGAL ACTIVITY) SS

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Article Received on 19 Feb. 2026,
Article Revised on 11 March 2026,
Article Published on 01 April 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19327712>

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How to cite this Article: *¹Iyswarya S.,
²Sakthivel M., ³Mohamed Halith S.,
⁴Purushothaman S., ⁴Raghavi V., ⁴Ragupathi R.,
⁴Rajesh R., ⁴Rajesh Kanna R. (2026).
Formulation And Characterization Of
Clotrimazole Oro-Retentive Gummies For The
Treatment Of Oral Candidiasis (Anti-Fungal
Activity) Ss World Journal of Pharmacy and
Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(4), 416–432.
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ABSTRACT

Chewable Gummy Tablets (CGTs), also known as a gummy confection or confectionery gel, consists of sucrose or syrup combined with a gelling agent such as gelatin. Other excipients can be added to this formulation, including coloring agent, flavor and acidulant. Nowadays, CGTs have been developed as nutraceutical products since these are easier to swallow or chew compared to other dosage forms like tablets or capsules. Therefore, they are widely used in pediatric, geriatric and patients with swallowing problems. CGTs are formulated using a gelling agent as the vehicle of this product. Several hydrocolloid substances serve as gelling agents, such as gelatin, sodium alginate and gum. The selection of a gelling agent is a pivotal part of CGTs formulation because it significantly affects the physicochemical properties of these products. Chewable tablets are a versatile dosage form offering several advantages including oral drug delivery without the need for water, ease of swallowing, the stability advantages of solid

dosage forms, and planetocentric drug delivery, they provide a convenient means of pediatric drug delivery and the delivery of nutritional products such as chewable multivitamins. As a dosage form, chewable tablets have the advantages of conventional tablets in terms of manufacturability, dosing accuracy, portability, and long-term stability. Additionally, chewable tablets facilitate swallowing as the product is initially broken low into particles in the oral cavity. This is a useful patient-centric advantage for populations such as pediatrics for whom swallowing conventional tablets is a concern. As water is not required for their administration, there is a benefit of convenience when dosing, Despite the widespread use of chewable tablets there have been few comprehensive publications about them since the work of Mendes *et al.* in 1989. FDA published guidance in 2018 on quality attribute considerations for chewable tablets.

INTRODUCTION

Medicated chewing gums are solid, single dose preparations that contain one or more active ingredients that are released by chewing. This drug delivery system provides additional patient benefits and compliance, offering several advantages over tablets or liquid formulations in that, the therapeutic system is not be swallowed and this increases patient compliance, especially for geriatrics and pediatrics with swallowing disorders, moreover, the product can be taken anywhere and at any time as it does not require liquids to aid swallowing.

Most of the drug released from the gum through mastication is rapidly absorbed via the buccal cavity due to its large vascularization; therefore, a faster absorption results in a shorter duration of action. Alternatively, drug released from medicated chewing gum which is not absorbed through the oral cavity membranes will be swallowed and reach the stomach in a very fine dispersed form, thus being easily available for gastrointestinal absorption with a consequent fast onset of action. The oral mucosa is highly perfused with blood vessels having a blood flow of 20-30 ml/ min for each 100g of tissue. Drugs absorbed via the buccal cavity have direct access to the systemic circulation which bypasses intestinal and hepatic first- pass metabolism, thus potentially increasing their extent of absorption.

MATERIALS AND METHOD OF PREPARATION**Table 1: LIST OF CHEMICALS.****Gelatin based clotrimazole chewable gummy tablet formula (For 15 tablets)**

S.NO	CHEMICALS NAME	VENDORS
1	Clotrimazole drug	Halcyon lab pvt. ltd
2	Ethanol	Halcyon lab pvt. ltd
3	Gelatin	Halcyon lab pvt. ltd
4	Sorbitol	Halcyon lab pvt. ltd
5	Citric acid	Halcyon lab pvt. ltd
6	Sodium benzoate	Halcyon lab pvt. ltd
7	Propylene glycol	Halcyon lab pvt. ltd
8	Glycerin	Halcyon lab pvt. ltd

INGREDIENTS**Peppermint**

Peppermint is used to add flavor or fragrance to foods, cosmetics, soaps, toothpaste, mouthwashes, and other products, and it may have some medicinal uses.

Sodium benzoate

Sodium benzoate inhibits the growth of potentially harmful bacteria, mold, and other microbes in food, thus deterring spoilage.

It is used to absorb extra water and maintain moisture in certain medicines, cosmetics, or food products. It is a solvent for food colors and flavors.

Citric acid

Because of its acidic, sour-tasting nature, citric acid is predominantly used as a flavoring and preserving agent, especially in soft drinks and candies. It's also used to stabilize or preserve medicines.

Sucrose

Sucrose, a disaccharide, is a sugar composed of glucose and fructose subunits. It is produced naturally in plants and is the main constituent of white sugar.

Menthol

Menthol is a type of sugar alcohol used as a sweetener and medication. It is used as a low calories sweetener as it is poorly absorbed by the intestines.

COLLECTION OF CLOTRIMAZOLE

Clotrimazole was received as a gift sample from Halcyon lab pvt. ltd, Naroda, Ahmedabad, India. White beeswax was received as a gift sample from Arjuna Beeswax Industries, Virar, Palghar. Kollidon was received as a gift sample from BASF India Limited, Belapur, Navi Mumbai, India. Mannitol as a sweetener and menthol as a flavouring agent was received as a gift sample from Vishal Chemicals, Navi Mumbai, India. All other chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade.

PREPARATION OF CLOTRIMAZOLE SOLUTION

Weigh accurately 50mg of drug and transfer it into 50ml of volumetric flask with methanol. From the stock solution withdraw 10ml and make up with methanol in 100ml of volumetric flask. Withdraw 1ml, 2ml, 3ml, 4ml of solution from 100ml of the volumetric flask and make up with water up to 10ml. Methanol and water mixture was used as a solvent for the UV spectrometer for the drug content of clotrimazole at 2.25g.

Clotrimazole standard curve in Phosphate buffer Ph 6.8 Weigh accurately 5mg of drug and transfer it into 50ml volumetric flask and make up the volume using solvent system containing 20 % methanol 40% Phosphate buffer Ph 6.8, 40% PEG. Mixture was sonicated for 10 minutes till dissolved. Then 2. 4. 6. 8. 10 ml of this solution was withdrawn and diluted up to 100ml in volumetric flask. Absorbance of these samples (n=3) were measured at 310 nm using UV Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV 1800) The standard curve was plotted after obtaining the mean absorbance, and the linear equation was achieved.

For 15 gummy tablet weigh accurately 2.25g of clotrimazole in menthol standard curve.

GELATIN BASED CHEWABLE GUMMY TABLET PREPARATION

Gelatin based of clotrimazole were prepared by heating and congealing. Three formulas were developed in this study Gelatin is used as a gelling agent with three different concentrations: 5%, 7.5%, 10%. Gelatin as gelling agents play a pivotal role in the formula.

Sucrose served as a sweetening agent and enhanced the 3D gel structure with gelling agent and water. Mannitol has a role, not only to increase acceptability but also as a firming agent. A firming agent was used in chewable gummy tablets to increase the hardness of the tablet. Citric acid was used in this formula as an acidulant to increase the acceptability of this product. Sodium benzoate serves as preservatives; hence propylene glycol has a function to

increase the elasticity of the chewable gummy. Peppermint oil flavour and coloring agents were also used in this study to increase customer perception and preference. To prevent the chewable stuck in the mold, corn oil was utilized in this study.

Procedure for chewable gummy

The step started with clotrimazole powder with propylene glycol in a 1:5 ratio (w/w), followed by dispersing the moistened powder in 30 ml of purified water.

An accurate amount of sucrose was dissolved in hot purified water (80°C) and continuously stirred in a mixing pan. Mannitol was mixed with liquid paraffin, then this mixture was added to the sucrose solution. Gelling agent (gelatin) was added to the mixture gradually and uniformly while stirred homogenous dispersions were observed. Subsequently, propylene glycol was added to the mixture while stirred continuously.

Citric acid, sodium benzoate, peppermint oil, and coloring agent were dissolved separately in hot water, and then the resulted solutions were first mixed before being added to the previous mixture with continuous stirring at 80°C. When the temperature of the mixture reached 60°C, the dispersed Citrulluscolocynthis fruit powder was poured gradually into the mixture then stirred homogeneously for 10 minutes. The mixture obtained was then poured into the jelly mold and stored in an airtight container at room temperature (25– 30°C) for 24 hours to harden to CGTs. These CGTs were then packed individuals in aluminum foil paper and stored in an at jar for further analyses, including physical characteristics evaluation.

Table 2: Gelatin based clotrimazole chewable gummy tablet formula (For 15 tablets)

INGREDIENTS	FORMULA 01	FORMULA 02	FORMULA 03
Clotrimazole drug	2.25g	2.25g	2.25g
Ethanol	10ml	12ml	16ml
Gelatin	16g	18g	20g
Sorbitol	5ml	5ml	5ml
Citric acid	0.1g	0.1g	0.1g
Sodium benzoate	0.005ml	0.005ml	0.005ml
Propylene glycol	0.04ml	0.04ml	0.04ml
Glycerin	5ml	5ml	5ml
Sugar	12g	15g	18g
Water	45ml	50ml	55ml

EVALUATION OF MEDICATED CHEWABLE GUMMIES

1. Organoleptic Observations

The prepared clotrimazole gummy tablet were observed organoleptically for color, taste,

shape, texture, and clarity. The texture observation was conducted by mildly rubbing the surface and rubbing the tablets between two fingers.

2. Weight Variation Test

Weight variation of the CGTs was measured to determine the content homogeneity of each tablet. In the initial stage, not less than 15 individual tablets were weighed, and then the average weight was calculated. The tablet is concluded as meeting the predefined requirement if its weight does not deviate more than 7.5% from the average. If one tablet fell outside this range, the test continued to the second stage with an additional set of not less than 15 CGTs the test continued to the second stage with an additional set of not less than 15 CGTs, in which the tablet is concluded as meeting the requirement if its weight does not deviate more than 10% from the average weight.

3. Disintegration test

The disintegration test is to evaluate the ability of a sample to break into smaller particles under standard conditions. The test is usually performed on tablets, capsules, and enteric-coated tablets, and it provides critical safety data on bioavailability of drugs in vivo without the use of in vivo methods. Ther disintegration testing is very important for oral formulations.

The mean disintegration times ranged from 6 to more than 60 min in distilled water and from 9 to over 60 min in 0.1N HCl. The products with longer disintegration times had higher breaking force and tensile strength values.

4. Dissolution test

Dissolution testing for chewable gummies involves assessing how well the active ingredients released when the gummy is chewed exposed to saliva .it ensures that the ingredients are effectively available for absorption.

The test typically considers factors such as disintegration time and dissolution profile. The dissolution gummy is an importance consideration when evaluating there effectiveness manufacture needed to ensure that there product dissolve quickly effectively in the mouth to ensure fast absorbance of their active ingredient and optimal therapeutic effect Coated tablet introduce one tablet into each of the six tubes, add disc to each tube, and operate the apparatus, using water as the immersion fluid. Unless otherwise stated in the individual monograph film-coated tablets disintegrate within 30 minutes and other coated tablets

disintegrate within 60 minutes.

5. UV Spectrophotometry

UV spectrophotometry is a reliable, rapid, and economical analytical technique used to quantify antifungal drugs-such as clotrimazole-in oral formulations for treating oral candidiasis. It enables precise drug estimation, typically validating drug content with high recovery rates and enabling the development of mucoadhesive or sustained- release delivery systems.

6. Antifungal Activity

Oral candidiasis, commonly caused by *Candida albicans*, is effectively treated with topical antifungals like Wave number oral agents such as clotrimazole for severe cases. These treatments target fungal cell membranes, but rising resistance has led to increased use of alternatives like echinocandins, amphotericin B, and natural products.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. ORGANOLEPTIC PROPERTIES

This study prepared CGTs containing clotrimazole powder using gelatin as the gelling agent. Organoleptically, all CGTs had a shape, light pink color, peppermint aroma, and sweet taste. This homogenous appearance has a positive impact on consumer perception and acceptance.

The texture was non-sticky, elastic and chewy, with adequate gel strength. A higher gelling agent concentration means higher mechanical strength and, as a result, less elastic texture. Figure shows the physical appearance of the prepared gelatin based CGTs.

S.NO	FORMULA01	FORMULA02	FORMULA03	FORMULA04
1	Shape	Round flower shape	Round flower shape	Round flower shape
2	Color	Light pink color	Light pink color	Light pink color
3	Flavor	Peppermint	Peppermint	Peppermint
4	Taste	characteristics	characteristics	characteristics
5	Texture	Non sticky less elastic	Non sticky less elastic	Non sticky less elastic

2. WEIGHT VARIATION TEST

All of the prepared CGTs in this study weighed between 6 and 6.1grams. The results showed that no individual tablet exceeded the weight in the pharmacopoeia requirement, implying that all the prepared tablets contain a homogenous amount of clotrimazole powder and the gelatin performed the desired function as gelling agents to produce homogeneity.

Also, a further physical evaluation revealed that the dimension of the prepared formulation deviated within the specific range.

FORMULATION 01

NUMBER OF TABLET	WEIGHT OF TABLET
1	6.00gm
2	6.09gm
3	6.07gm
4	6.01gm
5	5.99gm
6	6.04gm
7	6.02gm
8	6.04gm
9	6.03gm
10	5.99gm
11	6.04gm
12	6.11gm
13	6.01gm
14	6.00gm
15	6.02gm
AVERAGE VALUE	6.08gm

(The weight variation of chewable gummy is 1.08gm)

FORMULATION 02

NUMBER OF TABLET	WEIGHT OF TABLET
1	6.12gm
2	6.18gm
3	6.08gm
4	6.06gm
5	6.00gm
6	5.97gm
7	6.00gm
8	5.96gm
9	6.04gm
10	6.03gm
11	6.09gm
12	6.14gm
13	6.06gm
14	6.00gm
15	6.05gm
AVERAGE VALUE	6.05gm

(The weight variation of chewable gummy is 6.05gm)

FORMULATION 03

NUMBER OF TABLET	WEIGHT OF TABLET
1	6.02gm
2	5.96gm
3	6.17gm
4	6.02gm
5	6.07gm
6	5.99gm
7	5.95gm
8	6.06gm
9	5.04gm
10	6.09gm
11	6.04gm
12	6.08gm
13	6.02gm
14	6.03gm
15	6.02gm
AVERAGE VALUE	6.02gm

(THE weight variation of chewable gummy is 6.02) The CGT passes the weight variation test.

Average weight = 6.08

$$6.08 \times 5 \sqrt{100} = 0.026$$

$$6.08 \pm 0.026$$

Weight variation is 6.024g to 6.134

UV-visible spectrophotometry

UV-visible spectrophotometric analysis was conducted on the sample using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer, USA Model: Lambda 950) with a slit width of 2nm, using a 10-mm cell at room temperature. The extract was examined under visible and UV light in the wavelength ranging from 300-800nm for proximate analysis. For UV-VIS spectrophotometer analysis, the extract was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min and filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The sample is diluted to 1:10 with the same solvent (Karpagasundari et al., 2014).

Table 1: UV-VIS peak values of Clotrimazole Drug.

S.NO	Wavelength (nm)	Absorbance
1	227.0	4.000

UV analysis of Jelly sample

Table 2: UV-VIS peak values of Jelly sample.

S.NO	Wavelength (nm)	Absorbance
1	225.2	4.000
2	236.0	3.363
3	254.0	2.911

Invitro drug Release Profile

In vitro dissolution studies

In vitro dissolution studies of Oro retentive jelly of Clotrimazole were carried out in USP tablet dissolution test apparatus-II, employing a paddle stirrer at 50 rpm using 900 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ as dissolution medium. One jelly was placed in each vessel. At

predetermined time intervals for 5, 10, 15, 30, 45 and 60 minutes, 5 ml of the samples were withdrawn by means of a syringe and the volume withdrawn at each interval was replaced with same quantity of fresh dissolution medium. The samples were analysed for drug release by measuring the absorbance at 227 nm using UV spectrophotometer. The drug concentration was calculated from the calibration curve of drug.

$$\text{Concentration } (\mu\text{g/mL}) = \frac{\text{Absorbance} - c}{m}$$

Where:

- m = slope of calibration curve
- c = intercept of calibration curve

Amount of Drug Released (mg)

$$\text{Drug released (mg)} = \text{Concentration } (\mu\text{g/mL}) \times \text{Volume of dissolution medium (mL)} \div 1000$$

Cumulative Percentage Drug Release

$$\text{Cumulative \% Drug Release} = \frac{\text{Cumulative amount of drug released}}{\text{Total drug content}} \times 100$$

Where:

- Total drug content = 10 mg clotrimazole

RESULTS

Time (min)	Absorbance	Drug released (mg)	Cumulative % drug release
5	0.051	0.51	5.1 ± 0.5
10	0.112	1.12	11.2 ± 0.7
15	0.184	1.84	18.4 ± 0.9
30	0.312	3.12	31.2 ± 1.1
45	0.441	4.41	44.1 ± 1.31
60	0.586	5.86	58.6 ± 1.5

In Vitro Buccal Adsorption Study⁰

Preparation of Buccal Mucosa

1. Fresh buccal mucosa was obtained from a local slaughterhouse.
2. The tissue was washed thoroughly with distilled water and PBS (pH 6.8).
3. Adhering fat and connective tissue were carefully removed.
4. The mucosa was stored in PBS at 4 °C and used within 24 hours.

Procedure

Mounting of Buccal Mucosa

1. Mount the buccal mucosa between donor and receptor compartments of the Franz cell.
2. Ensure the epithelial side faces the donor compartment.
3. Avoid air bubble formation.
4. Loading of Receptor Compartment
5. Fill receptor compartment with phosphate buffer pH 7.4 containing 1% methanol.
6. Maintain temperature at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ with continuous stirring.

Application of Jelly

7. Accurately weigh 1 g of clotrimazole jelly and place uniformly on the mucosal surface in the donor compartment.
8. Cover donor compartment to prevent evaporation.

Sampling

9. Withdraw 1 mL samples from receptor compartment at:
 1. 5, 10, 15, 30, 45, 60, 90, 120 minutes
10. Replace each withdrawn volume with equal amount of fresh pre-warmed buffer.

Analysis

11. Filter samples using 0.45 µm membrane filter.
12. Analyse at 261 nm by UV spectrophotometry.
13. Calculate drug concentration using calibration curve.

Determination of Drug Adsorption

1. The concentration of Clotrimazole in the buffer was determined using a UV–Visible spectrophotometer at its λ max.
2. The amount of drug adsorbed onto the buccal mucosa was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Drug adsorbed (mg)} = \text{Initial drug amount} - \text{Drug remaining in solution}$$

3. Percentage drug adsorption was calculated as:

$$\% \text{ Drug Adsorbed} = \frac{\text{Drug adsorbed}}{\text{Initial drug amount}} \times 100$$

RESULTS

Time (min)	Initial Drug Conc. (mg)	Final Drug Conc. (mg)	Drug Adsorbed (mg)	% Buccal Adsorption
5	10.0	9.4	0.6	6.0 ± 0.26
10	10.0	8.8	1.2	12.0 ± 1.8
15	10.0	8.1	1.9	19.0 ± 1.05
30	10.0	6.7	3.3	33.0 ± 1.52
45	10.0	5.4	4.6	46.0 ± 1.42
60	10.0	4.0	6.0	60.0 ± 1.6

Antifungal Activity

Preparation of Fungal strains

Candida albicans (MTCC 183), obtained from the Microbial Type Culture Collection (IMTECH, Chandigarh, India). The fungal strains were cultured in Potato Dextrose Broth at 37°C for 24 hr.

Agar Well Diffusion Method

The antimicrobial activity of sample against the *Candida albicans* was carried out using Agar Well Diffusion Susceptibility Test Method followed by NCCLS (1993) and Awoyinka *et al.*, (2007). The microbial strains were spread on the Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) (Merck, Germany) using sterile cotton swab. Using sterile micropipette load the well with 25, 50 and 100 µl of sample and standard solution as Fluconazole 30µl were laid down on the inoculated agar plate. The plates were incubated at 27°C for 48 hr. for yeast strains. Sample was tested in triplicate.

Antifungal activity of given sample using agar well diffusion method.

S. No	Name of the Organisms	Sample Jelly (Zone of Inhibition [mm])			
		Positive control Fluconazole (30µg)	25 µl	50 µl	100 µl
FUNGAL STRAIN					
1	<i>Candida albicans</i>	23 ± 0.32	11 ± 2.5	13 ± 3.25	15 ± 2.41

Values expressed as Mean ± SD for triplicates, Standard: Chloramphenicol (Bacteria), Fluconazole (Fungal); mm: Milli meter.

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CONCLUSION

Chewable Gummy tablet not only offers clinical benefits but also is an attractive, discrete, and efficient drug Delivery system. Thus, it can be said that gum sticks can be utilized as a drug delivery system for a wide range of medications that require both local and prolonged release. Chewable gummy tablet can be used whenever you want, even without water. Medicated gummy tablet have the potential for both local and systemic impacts on oral mucosa. They can also be used to disguise the taste of some medications.

However, clotrimazole chewable gummy tablets are thought to demonstrate their position as a practical and advantageous medication delivery because they adhere to the strict pharmaceutical quality standards to obtain various active component release profiles.

The conclusion of the research was to study the anti-alopecia activity of clotrimazole chewable gummy tablets. The developed chewable gummy tablet was evaluated by organoleptic property, weight variation test, swelling ratio test, Disintegration time test, texture analysis and invitro dissolution test.

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